

GNSS Jamming Detection by Detection of Pseudorange Noise

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1 Abstract

The vulnerability of Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) to jamming necessitates robust detection methods that can trigger before a receiver loses lock. This paper investigates a novel jamming detection technique based on spectral analysis of pseudorange noise. The method operates by comparing the high-frequency (0.15–0.5 Hz) energy of the pseudorange signal during periods of suspected jamming to a baseline clean period. An energy increase beyond a defined threshold triggers a jamming declaration. The algorithm was evaluated using data from a controlled field trial. The best observed performance, achieved through selective satellite pairing, yielded a false positive rate of 6.2% and a false negative rate of 21.1%. However, these results are based on a limited dataset not originally intended for this analysis, leading to wide confidence intervals. We conclude that while the method shows significant promise, its performance is not yet fully characterized. Future work involving larger datasets, machine learning optimization, and fusion with other detection methods (e.g., C/N₀ monitoring) is recommended to mature this approach into a reliable defensive tool.

Keywords: *Jamming, detection, pseudorange, Global Navigation Satellite Systems*

2 Introduction

Jamming of GPS/GNSS signals is a real and growing threat. Popular media reports indicate that the use of GNSS jamming is widespread in the current Ukraine conflict and in Eastern Europe [3]. Due to the heavy reliance of civil aviation navigation on GNSS, jamming of GNSS signals has high potential for catastrophic consequences. Use of jamming devices in conflict situations has become so common that defence manufacturers are now making seekers that home on GPS jamming emitters in order to destroy them and eliminate the threat they pose to GPS guided munitions [1].

It would be highly desirable to be able to detect the presence of GNSS jamming before the jamming renders the receiver inoperable. Practical experience with GPS receivers indicates that they do not show a graceful degradation in position accuracy as jamming increases in intensity. Instead, their reporting becomes intermittent, then suddenly fails. Detection of jamming either by degradation of position accuracy, or by observing a loss of data is therefore not a practical option. At the point where data stops flowing from the receiver, it is far too late for the platform mounting the receiver to take any useful mitigating action.

Detection of an electronic attack when the receiver is within the field of influence of the jammer but before it drops out would be far more useful. This would give forewarning of hostile jamming activity, which could be a precursor to a kinetic attack or some other type of hostile activity.

The detection method that we report here is by no means perfect. Since it is independent of other proposed methods that rely on changes in C/N0 or automatic gain control [5, 6], we believe it will be a valuable addition to the tool set in detecting attack on GNSS signals.

Jada et al examined jamming detection by a loss of C/N0 [2]. Jada used real world data from reference receivers in the US National Positioning Infrastructure as a data source. This identified a number of events that were highly consistent with a jamming signal in the vicinity of the reference receiver. In some cases, they were able to correlate suspected jamming events with other events, including military GPS testing events, and a loss of navigation integrity category reported in ADS-B data. They did not have a controlled environment, so were unable to confirm if and when they made a correct declaration of jamming.

Balaei and Dempster [9] used a software receiver that made the IF signal available for post processing prior to correlation with the satellite pseudorandom noise code. Similar to the approach here, they determined the power in a number of frequency bins during a known interference free period, then did the same during a suspected jamming period. Presence of interference was detected by an increase in power in a frequency bin. Balaei and Dempster only tested their method with CW interference, so it may not be robust against wideband interference. The method is not specific to GNSS, so would be effective with any signal that has a stationary spectrum. The main disadvantage of the method is its high computational burden. Balaei and Dempster report processing times of up to five minutes. The method proposed here has a much lower computational burden, but is not as reliable.

In contrast to these approaches, the analysis of pseudorange noise in the frequency domain for jamming detection appears to be an unexplored area. This paper aims to fill this gap.

Section 3 of this paper explains the algorithm, how the data was analysed, and provides a rationale for some of the choices of parameters in the algorithm. Section 4 presents an overview of the results that were obtained from the data, including false positive/negative rates of the algorithm, and 95% confidence intervals of those rates. Section 5 discusses the results of the analysis and provides suggestions of where future work in this area could be directed. Section 6 gives our conclusions.

3 Methodology

3.1 Background

Similar to Jada [2], the proposition that we investigate here is that jamming of GNSS signals can be detected before a receiver drops out by measuring the “high frequency” noise in the pseudorange signal reported by a RINEX GNSS receiver. Here, “high frequency” means the noise in the reported pseudorange signal in the range 0.15 – 0.5Hz, where the pseudorange signal is reported at 1s intervals.

This work emerged from a joint trial conducted by Defence Department and Geoscience Australia in November 2023. Three RINEX receivers were placed in an open field south of Canberra roughly 100m apart, and a jamming signal under the control of the test team was radiated to the open air at various distances. The jamming signal was designed to target the L1 and L2 frequencies used by GPS, 1575.42MHz and 1227.6MHz respectively. Data was collected from the RINEX receivers in both clean and jamming environments. The RINEX receivers were configured to collect data from all visible GNSS satellites.

Figure 1. Reported C/N0 for GLONASS R19

Figure 1 shows the reported C/N0 for a signal from a GLONASS satellite in the L1 band. Due to the carrier frequency of the GLONASS signal being higher than that of GPS, the jamming signal degrades the reception of the signal, but does not completely block reception.

When a RINEX receiver reports pseudorange of a satellite, it reports one pseudorange per signal generated by that satellite, which are not all equal to each other. Figure 2 shows the difference between the maximum and minimum reported pseudorange for the GLONASS R19 satellite during the one hour period 0000 – 0100Z based on the C1C and C1P signals. The periods of increased pseudorange variation align with the periods of decreased C/N0 in Figure 1 and with the log of jamming activity in the L1 band that was kept during the trial. Those periods were 0000 – 0005Z, 0018 – 0024Z and 0050 – 0055Z. The same variation was not observed in the difference between the L1C and L1P carrier phase signals.

Figure 2. Maximum to minimum variation in pseudorange of R19 GLONASS satellite

Increased noise in the pseudorange signal indicates that the presence of jamming could be detected by spectral analysis of the pseudorange signal. In this paper, we report on the results of our efforts to develop a jamming detector based on this method.

3.2 Mechanism of Action

A GNSS signal transmitted from a spacecraft is modulated with a direct sequence spread spectrum spreading code which is unique to each spacecraft. The receiver attempts to align a locally generated copy of this code with the received signal, thereby despreading it. This is what gives fine range resolution. We assume that this is a noisy process.

Figure 3 shows the spectral density of reported pseudorange of a typical signal. In the low frequency range of the pseudorange signal, the signal in the frequency domain is dominated by the relatively slow range variation of the satellite transmitting the signal. At higher frequencies, above 0.15Hz, the signal is dominated by noise. To detect an increase in noise in the reported pseudorange, it is necessary to look at frequencies above 0.15Hz. The detection algorithm presented here looks for an increase in the noise in this range.

Figure 3. Typical pseudorange spectral density

3.3 Algorithm

The algorithm works on data reported from a RINEX receiver reported at one second intervals.

1. Take 60s of continuous pseudorange data from any navigation satellite during a known clean/nonjamming period reported at 1s intervals.
2. Normalise the pseudorange to the range $-1 \dots +1$, to remove the low-frequency geometric range dynamics and isolate the noise. This allows two different satellites at different ranges to be compared.
3. Apply a Tukey window that tapers the first 5% and the last 5% of the signal to 0.
4. Calculate the power spectral density of the signal in (3).
5. Calculate A = energy of (4) integrated between 0.15 and 0.5Hz. The choice of 0.15Hz is explained in section 3.2.
6. Repeat (1) – (4) for another pseudorange signal during a suspected jamming period.
7. Calculate B = energy of (6) integrated between 0.15 and 0.5Hz.
8. Calculate $C = (B - A) / A$.
9. If $C > 2$ declare jamming is present. A threshold of $C > 2$ was selected based on an analysis of the receiver operating characteristic, as detailed in the Results section.

3.4 Analysis

We developed an application to implement the above algorithm in Matlab. The algorithm does not work if either of the satellites crosses zenith during the 60s analysis period. A

robust implementation of this algorithm would reject such satellites from selection. This selection strategy has not been implemented in our application, where satellites are selected manually on an opportunity basis. This does not limit the usefulness of this algorithm, as there are around thirty GNSS satellites visible in the sky at any given time, few if any of which are crossing zenith.

Figure 4 shows a screen shot of the application, showing a subset of the GNSS signals that were captured by the RINEX receiver during a one hour period. Observation codes are those defined in the RINEX standard [4].

Figure 4. Analyser signal selection tab

Figure 5 shows the tab for selection of time to be detected for jamming, and satellite and signal to be analysed.

Figure 5. Analyser satellite selection tab

We have generated 378 data points by applying the above algorithm at arbitrarily selected times using various combinations of the available signals. We then filtered those results based on various selection criteria such as constellation and elevation angle. Results were tallied up and scored in a separate Matlab script that reported false positive and false negative rates.

We determined the 95% confidence interval of false positive and false negative rates by assuming that the outcome of the assessment was binomially distributed and calculating the Wilson interval of the estimated probability [8]. If the upper limit of the 95% confidence interval exceeds 0.5, the method is no better than tossing a coin and needs further refinement.

The influence of satellite elevation on accuracy was investigated. We obtained historic orbital parameters in the form of two line element files for the observed satellites by special request from celestrak.org [7]. This produced reliable results for the GPS and Galileo constellations, but for the other constellations it was not possible to match a NORAD catalogue number with a reporting number in the data. The resulting data set where elevation of a satellite is positively identified is very limited and did not allow us to determine the influence of elevation angle on performance, if any.

4 Results

Data collected during the trial creates a large number of possible combinations of jamming and non-jamming periods and satellites that could be used in the algorithm at 3.3. We have not attempted to analyse all possible combinations. As the trial was not designed to create data for such an analysis, we believe that doing so is likely to lead to a biased result and an incorrect view of the algorithm's performance. Instead, we present the following results generated by a manual/heuristic selection of jamming and non-jamming times.

To justify the selection of $C = 2$ as the decision threshold in step 9 of the algorithm, we examined the false positive and negative rates as a function of the decision threshold. Figure 6 shows the false positive, false negative and their sum as a function of the decision threshold. The sum of the two false rates reaches a global minimum at $C = 2$.

Figure 6. False detection rate as a function detection threshold

A subset of the results is presented in Table 1, highlighting configurations that yielded the lowest error rates. The full set of results is available in the appendix. The wide confidence intervals, particularly for configurations with fewer data points, indicate that a larger dataset is required to draw definitive conclusions about the optimal satellite selection strategy.

Filtering applied	False positive rate		False negative rate	
	Observed rate, 95% CI	Number of data points	Observed rate, 95% CI	Number of data points.
No filtering	0.231, 0.170 – 0.306	147	0.338, 0.280 – 0.401	231
Noisy = GLONASS only Clean = GLONASS only	0.280, 0.195 – 0.386	82	0.211, 0.149 – 0.292	123
Noisy = GLONASS only Clean = GPS only	0.062, 0.011 – 0.283	16	0.412, 0.264 – 0.578	34
Noisy elevation > 0° Clean elevation > 15°	0.118, 0.055 – 0.234	51	0.485, 0.368 – 0.603	66

Table 1. False positive and false negative rates for the algorithm

5 Discussion

The best observed false positive rate was 0.062, which was created by using a GPS satellite as the clean signal (steps 1 – 4 of the algorithm) and a GLONASS satellite as the noisy signal (step 6 of the algorithm). Which particular satellites were chosen was only on an opportunistic basis from the available data and not according to any rules. We suspect that with more research and a broader data set, better rules for selection of satellites could be developed.

Results could also be dependent on the waveform, i.e. centre frequency and bandwidth of the jammer. This was the result for the waveform of the particular jammer that was used at the trial. A different jammer with a centre frequency that targetted the frequencies used by GLONASS would likely give a different result.

As stated earlier, the limited data set available to us to perform this analysis does not allow us to fully characterise and optimise the algorithm. Ideally, we would generate a large data set of RINEX files in lab conditions that could be analysed and exploited for their data content. This would narrow the 95% confidence interval of the false positive and negative rates.

5.1 Influence of Elevation

From the results in Table 1, it appears that the algorithm favours the use of reference satellites that have a high elevation, although with the limited data available, it is difficult to make this statement with any certainty. The influence of the elevation of the noisy satellite is not particularly clear from the results.

Satellite elevation is a proxy measure for distance travelled through the ionosphere, which is anisotropic and inhomogeneous and which varies with time of day and a range of other factors. It is quite likely that these as yet unidentified factors will have an influence on the results of this algorithm.

Similarly, the influence of making intra- and inter-constellation comparisons is not particularly clear from the data. These and other confounding variables are listed below.

We are concerned about the upper range of the 95% CI for many of the results presented in Table 1. Any method where the upper end of the CI exceeds 0.5 is far too uncertain to be of any operational use. We further submit that a CI as high as 0.3, while better than tossing a coin, is also not particularly useful and would quickly fall into disuse.

Collection of further data would narrow the 95% CI range. For instance, the false negative rate of the GLONASS/GLONASS comparison was 0.211, based on 123 data points collected, giving a CI range of 0.189 – 0.235. If one hundred times as much data was collected, the CI range would reduce to 0.204 – 0.219, assuming the same failure rate.

5.2 Real Time Implementation

Running the algorithm described here takes less than one second on a laptop computer when running as a Matlab script. Based on this, we do not believe that it would impose a high CPU burden if it was implemented as an executable application. When running on a military platform it could be hosted on an unclassified virtual machine. Running the algorithm every ten seconds would be quite adequate for jamming detection purposes. The reporting latency would be around sixty seconds, which is the data collection period. For the majority of platforms, a sixty second latency period would be adequate for operations. For a platform that is a kinetic weapon operating at high speed and with limited human control, it may be too slow.

5.3 Machine Learning

As we have stated, there are many combinations of satellite, carrier and time parameters that could be explored to optimise the performance of the algorithm. The limited data set available to us prevents us from conducting such exploration. If such an expanded data set could be generated, we think it would be appropriate to extract performance parameters from it and feed those parameters into a machine learning algorithm. This would identify the optimum combination of parameters that would minimise false positive and false negative rates.

The performance figures in Table 1 indicate that processing GLONASS and GPS pseudorange achieves the lowest false positive rate, but also gives an unacceptably high false negative rate. It is apparent from this that no one combination of parameters will give an optimum result. The optimum strategy may be to make many different comparisons using different signals and conduct a “vote” of those combinations. The result of the vote would give the result, and a measure of the degree of confidence in it. Combining this with the C/N0 based algorithm of Jada [2] would provide an independent means of jamming detection, which would further improve confidence in the reported result.

5.4 Confounding Variables

To date, we have identified the following confounding variables, which are those which were not measured, or where insufficient data exists to characterise their influence.

- inter/intra constellation comparison
- satellite elevation
- inter/intra band comparison
- inter/intra signal comparisons
- age of reference satellite signal
- configuration parameters of the RINEX RX
- RINEX RX antenna pattern
- effect of multipath propagation
- state of the ionosphere

6 Conclusion

This paper has presented a proof-of-concept for a novel GNSS jamming detection method based on analyzing the spectral characteristics of pseudorange noise. The results from a limited field trial dataset are promising, indicating the potential for low false positive rates. However, the high false negative rates and wide confidence intervals underscore that the performance is not yet fully characterized and is highly dependent on satellite selection. The method's primary value lies in its independence from traditional C/N0-based techniques,

suggesting its ideal use would be in a multi-method fusion architecture. The most critical next step is the collection of a comprehensive, dedicated dataset to validate and optimize this approach, potentially using machine learning to manage the complex parameter space.

Future research in this area should focus on developing a sufficiently large dataset that can both validate the findings of this study and support statistically significant conclusions while also addressing the confounding variables identified above. With such a dataset, machine learning algorithms could be trained more effectively, allowing them to achieve optimized results.

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9 Appendix

The table below gives the false positive rate, false negative rate, 95% confidence intervals and number of data points for all filters applied to the data. Cells where the upper range of the confidence interval exceeds 0.5 are indicated in bold type.

Filtering applied	False positive rate		False negative rate	
	Observed rate, 95% CI	Number of data points	Observed rate, 95% CI	Number of data points.
No filtering	0.231, 0.170 – 0.306	147	0.338, 0.280 – 0.401	231
Noisy = all Clean = L1 band only	0.229 0.160 – 0.317	109	0.311 0.249 – 0.382	183
Noisy = L1 band only Clean = all	0.240 0.168 – 0.331	104	0.304 0.242 – 0.374	181
Noisy = L1 band only Clean = L1 band only	0.240 0.168 – 0.331	104	0.311 0.247 – 0.382	177
Noisy = all Clean = C1C signal only	0.170 0.109 – 0.255	100	0.328 0.262 – 0.400	174
Noisy = C1C signal only Clean = all	0.207 0.135 – 0.304	87	0.298 0.233 – 0.373	161
Noisy = C1C signal only Clean = C1C signal only	0.198 0.127 – 0.294	86	0.310 0.242 – 0.386	155
Noisy = GLONASS only Clean = all	0.235 0.164 – 0.326	102	0.282 0.219 – 0.356	163
Noisy = all Clean = GLONASS only	0.277 0.192 – 0.382	83	0.216 0.153 – 0.296	125
Noisy = GLONASS only Clean = GLONASS only	0.280 0.195 – 0.386	82	0.211 0.149 – 0.292	123
Noisy = GPS only Clean = all	0.161 0.071 – 0.326	31	0.444 0.246 – 0.663	18

Noisy = all Clean = GPS only	0.128 0.060 – 0.252	47	0.411 0.292 – 0.541	56
Noisy = GPS only Clean = GPS only	0.161 0.071 – 0.326	31	0.444 0.246 – 0.663	18
Noisy = GLONASS only Clean = GPS only	0.062 0.011 – 0.283	16	0.412 0.264 – 0.578	34
Noisy elevation > 15° Clean elevation > 0°	0.152 0.067 – 0.309	33	0.417 0.271 – 0.578	36
Noisy elevation > 30° Clean elevation > 0°	0.250 0.112 – 0.469	20	0.382 0.239 – 0.550	34
Noisy elevation > 45° Clean elevation > 0°	0.133 0.037 – 0.379	15	0.345 0.199 – 0.527	29
Noisy elevation > 0° Clean elevation > 15°	0.118 0.055 – 0.234	51	0.485 0.368 – 0.603	66
Noisy elevation > 0° Clean elevation > 30°	0.136 0.064 – 0.267	44	0.481 0.354 – 0.611	54
Noisy elevation > 0° Clean elevation > 45°	0.075 0.026 – 0.199	40	0.468 0.333 – 0.608	47
Noisy elevation > 15° Clean elevation > 15°	0.156 0.069 – 0.318	32	0.433 0.274 – 0.608	30
Noisy elevation > 30° Clean elevation > 30°	0.263 0.118 – 0.488	19	0.423 0.255 – 0.611	26
Noisy elevation > 45° Clean elevation > 45°	0.143 0.040 – 0.399	14	0.368 0.191 – 0.590	19